

ROLE OF AYURVEDA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF DANTAVESHTA (PYORRHOEA ALVEOLARIS)

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ABSTRACT

Oral health is an integral component of general health and plays a vital role in maintaining overall quality of life. Periodontal diseases are among the most prevalent oral disorders worldwide and significantly contribute to tooth loss.^[1] Dantaveshta, described under *Dantamulagata Rogas* in Ayurveda, is characterized by bleeding gums, pus discharge, inflammation, and mobility of teeth. It closely resembles Pyorrhoea Alveolaris described in modern dentistry.^[2] The present study was undertaken to evaluate the efficacy of Kanadi Churna Pratisarana and Madhu Mishrit Panchvalkal Kwatha Gandusha in the management of Dantaveshta. Clinical assessments showed significant improvement in signs and symptoms, indicating the effectiveness of Ayurvedic treatment modalities in periodontal disease.^[3]

KEYWORDS: Dantaveshta, Periodontitis, Pyorrhoea, Periodontium, Dantadhavana, Oral health.

INTRODUCTION

Oral health is an integral part of general well-being and is closely associated with the quality of life, extending beyond the functions of the craniofacial complex. Periodontal diseases are

among the most common global oral health problems. The prevalence of periodontal disease increases with age and has been reported as 57%, 67.7%, 89.6%, and 79.9% in the age groups of 12, 15, 35–44, and 65–74 years respectively.^[1]

In Ayurveda, diseases of the oral cavity are described under *Mukharogas*, among which *Dantamulagata Rogas* occupy an important place. Acharya Sushruta has described Dantaveshta as a condition characterized by bleeding gums, pus discharge, inflammation, and loosening of teeth due to vitiation of Kapha and Rakta Dosha.^[2]

Modern periodontal therapy mainly focuses on mechanical debridement and antimicrobial therapy, which often provide temporary relief and may be associated with side effects. Ayurveda offers a holistic and preventive approach using local therapeutic procedures such as *Pratisarana*, *Gandusha*, and herbal formulations that help in strengthening periodontal tissues and preventing disease progression.^[3]

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

AIM

To evaluate the role of Ayurvedic management in Dantaveshta (Pyorrhoea Alveolaris).

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the effect of Kanadi Churna Pratisarana in Dantaveshta.
2. To evaluate the efficacy of Madhu Mishrit Panchvalkal Kwatha Gandusha.
3. To establish a correlation between Dantaveshta and Pyorrhoea Alveolaris.^[4]

Inclusion Criteria

- Age group between 20–60 years
- Presence of classical symptoms of Dantaveshta
- Patients of both sexes.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients below 20 years
- Pregnant and lactating women
- Patients with systemic diseases such as diabetes, tuberculosis, HIV, or cardiovascular disorders.
- Patients with other Dantamulagata Rogas.^[5]

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Patients were assessed before and after treatment based on the following parameters:

1. Puyasrava (pus discharge)
2. Raktasrava (bleeding gums)
3. Chaladanta (tooth mobility)
4. Gingival inflammation

Clinical improvement was graded as cured, markedly improved, moderately improved, mildly improved, or unchanged.^[6]

DRUG REVIEW

- KANADI CHURNA for Pratisaran (yogratnakar) GROUP A:

KANADI CHURNA

➤ कणासिन्धुत्यजकाचूणण तूणं व्यपोहसत ।

घर्णणाद्दन्तचाञ्चल्यव्यथाशोथान्निखवान् । (yogratnakar)

It contains 3 drugs pippali, jeera, saindhava lavana.^[7]

GROUP B

Panchvalkal kwath for Gandhush (yogratnakar)

(गण्डूषे क्षीरिणो योज्याः सक्षौद्रधृतशर्कराः ।)

It contains are panchvalkal(vata, udambara, ashwatta, plaksha, parisha)^[8]

METHOD OF ADMINISTRATION

- **Kanadi Churna:** 3 g twice daily for Pratisarana
- **Panchvalkal Kwatha:** Gandusha with honey twice daily
- **Duration:** 15 days

Ingredients

KRISHNA JEERAKA

SAINDHAVA LAVANA

PIPPALI

Action

- Kapha-Rakta Shamana
- Shothahara
- Krimighna
- Strengthens gums and teeth.

Panchvalkal kwath will company then mixed be collected from GMP certified pharmaceutical with madhu. The kwath should be held in the mouth until full, without any movement inside. This process is known as "gandusha."

Dose of medicine

KanadiChurna- Approx 3gm.(Take it twice a day for 10 minutes each time, daily for 15 days.)
and Panchvalkal kwath- Shreshtha matra(full filled oral cavity twice daily for 15 days)

RESULTS

Significant improvement was observed in clinical parameters after treatment.

- Reduction in pus discharge – 52%
- Reduction in bleeding gums – 48%
- Reduction in tooth mobility – 45%
- Reduction in gingival inflammation – 52%

Overall, 80% of patients showed moderate improvement and 20% showed mild improvement. No adverse effects were reported.^[9]

DISCUSSION

Dantaveshta is caused by vitiation of Kapha and Rakta leading to inflammation, infection, and weakening of periodontal tissues. Kanadi Churna exhibits antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties, while Panchvalkal Kwatha promotes wound healing and tissue regeneration.^[10]

The procedures of Pratisarana and Gandusha improve local circulation, remove microbial load, and strengthen gingival tissues. The results of the study validate the classical Ayurvedic approach in managing periodontal diseases.^[11]

CONCLUSION

Dantaveshta, comparable to Pyorrhoea Alveolaris, is a chronic periodontal disease that can be effectively managed with Ayurvedic interventions. Kanadi Churna Pratisarana and Panchvalkal Kwatha Gandusha provide significant symptomatic relief, improve oral hygiene, and prevent disease progression. The therapy is safe, economical, and free from adverse effects, making it a valuable alternative in periodontal care.^[12]

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